

SEMANTIC TRANSFORMATION IN PHRASEOLOGY

Jumakulova Shakhnoza Kudrat kizi

Termez state university, Trainee-researcher of
the Department of English and Literature

E-mail: shaxnoz2023@mail.ru

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Abstract: This thesis discusses the phenomenon of semantic transformation that occurs in the formation of phraseological units. In addition, the meaning of phraseological units is explained and the phenomenon of semantic transformation in them is analyzed.

Key words: phraseology, phraseological unit, transformation, semantic transformation, partial semantic transformation.

Words are used to express people's thoughts. Expressing their meaning with phraseology increases effectiveness. Due to the presence of stylistic color in phraseologies, the content of sentences is enriched with their help. The formation of these phraseological units is related to the phenomenon of transformation, which is one of the urgent problems in linguistics.

According to H. Jamolkhanov, phraseology is a branch of linguistics that provides information about the phrases in the vocabulary of the language [4, 216]. Sh.Rakhmatullayev approves that this language unit is called in the literature by terms such as phraseologism, phraseological unit, lexeme, and phraseme, analogous to the terms morpheme [6, 420]. B.I.Boltayeva states that transformation (transposition) based on the use of language units (elements) in a non-specific function and meaning occurs as a free connection or a phraseological meaning that does not arise from the correct meaning of the sentence, and linguistic materials show that most of the phraseological units are formed on the basis of transformation (transposition) [1].

In addition, in the process of phraseological transformation, partial semantic reshaping, that is, the meaning of phraseological units occurs based on the figurative use or application of one component [1], B.I. Boltayeva explains and justifies with examples in her article.

In this research, phraseologies and their formation based on semantic transformation are explained and analyzed.

The phraseological unit "The joke is on someone" means "someone looks foolish, especially after trying to make someone else look so" [5, 156]. "The joke is on somebody" is formed on the basis of a complete semantic transformation, and its meaning is fully expressed figuratively.

The phraseological unit "good for a laugh" is interpreted as "guaranteed to amuse or entertain" [5, 168]. This phraseological unit "good for a laugh" is partially built on the basis of semantic transformation. If its "a laugh" part is expressed in its meaning, "good for" is used figuratively.

The phraseological unit "You are joking" means "used to show that you are very surprised at what somebody has just said" [3, 837]. This phraseological unit "you're joking" is made on the basis of a complete semantic transformation, and its meaning is used in a completely figurative sense.

The phraseological unit "Keep somebody amused" expresses the meaning of "to give somebody interesting things to do, or to entertain them so that they do not become bored" [3, 47]. This phraseological unit "keep somebody amused" is partially formed on the basis of semantic transformation. The word "amused" is used literally and the word "keep" is used figuratively.

"Grin and bear it" phraseological unit "if you are talking about a difficult situation and you say that someone will have to grin and bear it, you mean that they will have to accept it, because there is nothing they can do about it" [2, 170] explained by meaning. This phraseological unit "grin and bear it" was formed on the basis of a complete semantic transformation, and its meaning represents a fully transferred meaning.

From the above theoretical data and the results of the analysis, it can be concluded that the meaning expressed by the phraseological units is figurative and they are used partially or fully figuratively. The study of this phenomenon of semantic transformation in phraseological units is considered promising in the development of the field of lexicology.

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